

PRACTICAL SIGNIFICANCE OF PSYCHOLOGICAL STUDY OF PATIENTS INFECTED WITH VIRUS HEPATITIS C

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7561627>

Annotation: The article analyzes the content of medical reforms implemented in our country, the importance of psychological services in medicine, the role of psychological influence in medical diagnosis, psychological aspects of studying patients with VGS, the information obtained through clinical interviews with patients with VGS in our country.

Key words: concept, mental health, psychological service, quality of life, psychological impact, diagnosis, clinical interview, yatrogeniya, respondent.

Today, major reforms are being implemented in the field of health care in our country. Over the past three years, more than 150 legal documents have been adopted in the field of medicine. Including the "Concept of development of the healthcare system of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2019-2025" aimed at the fundamental reform of the medical system of Uzbekistan¹, Decisions on the confirmation of the concept of development of the mental health care service of the population of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2019-2025 have been developed. During the period of time spent in Concepcion, improvement of the national service for the protection of mental health of the population, implementation of specific works at all levels of the health care system to identify, treat and rehabilitate persons suffering from mental disorders, increase the capacity of personnel in the field of protection of the mental health of the population strengthening, special attention is paid to the training of specialists of the mental health protection service of the population in the directions of "medical psychologist and psychotherapist", "social work specialist", "social worker". This shows the serious attention paid not only to the field of medicine in our country, but also to the organization of psychological services in various fields of medicine².

Much attention is being paid to the study of infectious diseases, like all areas of medicine. Comprehensive measures to diagnose infectious diseases, including viral hepatitis in the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021, their prevention and further improvement of their treatment methods by the government of our country (No. 537 of the Cabinet of Ministers of July 24, 2017) decision) is a clear expression of this³.

This is because chronic viral hepatitis is one of the most common infectious diseases today. In addition to its widespread prevalence, the problematic nature of chronic viral hepatitis, the risk of complications and negative consequences are also associated with the defeat of people of the most working age. The high epidemic potential of these diseases remains not only in

¹ O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2018-yil 7-dekabrda PF-5590-son "O'zbekiston Respublikasi sog'liqni saqlash tizimini tubdan takomillashtirish bo'yicha kompleks chora- tadbirlar to'g'risida" gi farmoni

² O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 13.02.2019 yildagi PQ-4190-son "2019 — 2025-yillarda O'zbekiston Respublikasi aholisining ruhiy salomatligini muhofaza qilish xizmatini rivojlantirish konsepsiyasini tasdiqlash to'g'risidagi" qarori

³ O'zbekiston Respublikasi Vazirlar Mahkamasining 2017-yil 24-iyuldagi 537-son "O'zbekiston Respublikasida yuqumli kasalliklar tarqalishining oldini olishga doir qo'shimcha chora-tadbirlari to'g'risida"gi qarori

Uzbekistan, but throughout the world. In this sense, the problem of restoring the physical, mental and social condition of patients with chronic viral hepatitis has a national level.

Changes in mental status in most cases are one of the first manifestations of the disease, and often remain throughout the course of chronic viral hepatitis, which causes certain difficulties in the treatment of such patients.

In this regard, providing not only medical care, but also social psychological care to patients suffering from viral hepatitis C (HCV) is one of the urgent problems today. Because clinically significant emotional distress and depressive disorders, decreased quality of life have been reported in VGS patients, questioning the role of VGS in their occurrence⁴. Also, the disease is accompanied by complaints of malaise, depression, fatigue, discomfort in the musculoskeletal system and the upper right part of the abdomen, sleep disorders, decreased cognitive function, and mental dullness ("brain fog") A. Barkhuizen, H.R Rosen, D.M Forton, H.C. Thomas, S. Goulding, F.E. Murray's research has proven itself.

In a recent study by O. Dalgard, A. Egeland, and others, quality of life indicators in patients who were aware of the infection were significantly higher in 4 of the 8 SF-36 dimensions (general health, physical functioning, physical role, and vitality). was found to be lower than those who were not aware⁵. A.J. The results of the study by Rodger, D. Jolly, et al. showed that the diagnosis of VGS, even in the absence of serious liver disease, has a significant psychological and emotional burden. Therefore, it is determined that they should be taken into account when announcing the diagnosis of VGS in order to reduce its negative effects.⁶ The above shows that psychological influence can play an important role in medical diagnosis. Psychological research of patients infected with viral hepatitis C is of great importance. Because in patients with VGS, changes occur not only in the emotional sphere, but also in the social and personal sphere, and these changes depend on the level of the disease, the age of the patients, and individual typological characteristics. Preliminary observation and clinical interview are important in order to penetrate the inner world of patients to reveal the inner picture of the disease. Also, through the interview, trust and acceptance of the interlocutor is achieved in the person of the patient.

In this regard, in working with patients diagnosed with viral hepatitis C, following medical and psychological rules, initially clinical diagnostic observation and interview were used. In the process of observation and interview, special attention was paid to avoid iatrogenia (iatrogenia is a term that indicates a negative effect on the patient, in which instead of therapeutic effect, the patient creates ideas that aggravate the patient's disease condition, or a new mental, disease complex is formed⁷. Also, iatrogenic "negative psychotherapy"⁸ described as). These methods are designed to determine the condition of the examinees when the disease was diagnosed, the patient's physical ability and functional condition,

⁴ Forton DM, Taylor-Robinson SD, Thomas HC. Reduced quality of life in hepatitis C--is it all in the head. *J Hepatol.* 2002;**36**:435-438. [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]

⁵ Dalgard O, Egeland A, Skaug K, Vilimas K, Steen T. Health-related quality of life in active injecting drug users with and without chronic hepatitis C virus infection. *Hepatology.* 2004;**39**:74-80. [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]

⁶ Rodger AJ, Jolli D, Tompson SC, Lanigan A, Krofts N. Chronic hepatitis C virus infection leads to a significant reduction in quality of life in the absence of cirrhosis. *Hepatology.* 1998; **27**: 209-212

⁷ Ятрогенный (иатрогенный) //БМЭ,т.35, 1936, с . 816

⁸ *Каннабих Ю. В.* Врач как причина болезни // БМЭ, т. 5, 1928, с. 677—678.

psychological changes caused by the disease, and the meaning of life. 23 patients who were being treated at home and undergoing regular medical examinations took part in the experiment. (24-50 years old). The responses to each observation and interview question were mathematically processed and yielded the following results. During observation, a tendency to depression was found in the patients mainly based on emotional instability, anxiety, fear, aggression and stress. Especially in patients who have clear information about the disease, emotional states like the above were observed. Such cases are related to the stage of the disease, individual typological characteristics of the person, awareness of the etiology of the disease, attitude to the disease and many other factors.

How did you feel when you found out about your illness? 56.52% of the test takers were highly affected (stress, shock in the patient's language), 21.74% had strong anxiety and fear, 13.04% lacked confidence in the diagnosis, and 8.7% denied the disease. It can be seen that in the initial stage of the disease, mental tension, strong anxiety and fear occur in patients with hepatitis C. The following answers were received to the question, "Are you confident about your physical functions and abilities?" 69.57%, i.e. 16 patients answered "yes", 17.39% test subjects answered "no", only 3 people expressed partial concern. Patients who answered "I am not worried about my physical functions and abilities" said that they have a strong will.

The next question was "do you feel weak"? Those who do not feel weak strongly believe that they will recover. They answered, "If God wills, I will recover." It can be seen that hepatitis C causes a feeling of weakness in the patient. When the patients were asked about their awareness of the disease, that is, about the course of the disease, its consequences, the possibilities of its treatment, 43.48% of the patients were partially aware, 34.78% answered "yes", 13.04% were fully aware, 8.7 % said they were not aware at all. Other studies show that the awareness of the disease is one of the factors that reduce the quality of life of the patients. Also, the more information the patient has about the course of the disease, its negative consequences, treatment options, the less depression, anxiety, fear and similar diseases. negative emotional reactions have been found to have higher rates. "Do you regularly take medication? Do you know how they work, what to expect from them, and what side effects they have? The patients answered the question as follows. 82.61% of the examinees have knowledge about hepatitis C interferon injection therapy, surgical operation (liver transplantation), specific treatment of the disease (treatment with various special drugs), diet, daily routine and their side effects on the body. , that is, 19 of the respondents said yes, 17.39% -4 said they were not aware. Most of the test takers said that they have information about the negative effects of interferon injection therapy on the body. 73.91% of the respondents answered the question about their ability to talk about their illness with others, and 26.09% said that they could not talk to the interviewer. "Do you feel lonely?" the answers to the question were analyzed as follows. More than half of the patients, 52.17%, answered "no". They said that the love and attention of their loved ones and those around them increased especially when they were sick. 30.43% sometimes, 17.4% of test subjects feel completely alone. Also, it was revealed during the interview that most of the test subjects had difficulty and embarrassment in openly expressing their feelings and needs.

"What is the meaning of life for you?" almost half of the respondents, i.e. 47.83%, said health, 34.78% family, children, grandchildren maturity, 13.04% recovery, 4.35% life.

Test subjects said in the clinical diagnostic interview that the disease has fundamentally changed the meaning of the patients' lives, has created new approaches in their relationship

to the people around them and to life, and that the disease is a punishment or a test for them for some sin.

In conclusion, we can say that in the process of observation and clinical interview, the characteristics of the psychology of patients in the personal, social and emotional spheres are anxiety, fear, inability to openly express their needs, and the content of their lives is health-related. It has been. Also, patients suffering from this disease have a feeling of weakness in the personal and emotional spheres, feeling of weakness in the personal and emotional spheres, avoiding social relations due to the disease, dissatisfaction with their physical condition, depression, guilt, anxiety, and in some cases, isolation. characteristic was determined. So, psychological reactions in patients with VGS show significant changes. Including personal, emotional and volitional spheres. This, in turn, causes hepatitis C to be viewed as a highly stressful event with implications for patients' future health and behavior.

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